

Clock of the Universe

A model in which the position of stars relative to a fixed telescope on earth is recorded and passed through a mathematical model to estimate date and time to millisecond accuracy. The existing observatories cannot estimate date and time everyday from their observations. Presently it is a tedious and inaccurate method which is enhanced to millisecond accuracy with date and day included as per celestial positions of stars, sun etc celestial bodies. The project is classified under Systematic Invention Unit.

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The physical environment explains well behavior during these developments and phenomena. More people will derive information regarding their government. **High value** mechanical stress and physical space constraints within the...

